

MEDICAL SCIENCES

LONG-TERM OUTCOMES AFTER TIPS IN PATIENTS WITH BUDD-CHIARI SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

Budd Chiari syndrome is characterized as a group of heterogenous conditions of hepatic venous outflow obstruction (BCS) that is rare vascular disorder. Primary Budd-Chiari syndrome (BCS) is characterized by impairments of the right atrium and small hepatic veins at any level [1]. Most of myeloproliferative neoplasms and prothrombotic states are indications of early stages of BCS. With high death rates of 70% - 90%, BCS is a life-threatening disorder without treatment [2]. Long-terms outcomes after TIPS in patients with Budd-Chiari syndrome is discussed in this article.

Keywords: Budd-Chiari syndrome, meta-analysis, portal hypertension, liver diseases.

Introduction and Background.

The inferior veins (IVC) and right atrium might be the location of this venous blockage, as well as the small hepatic veins between each one. This definition does not include right-sided heart disease-related hepatic outflow obstruction or sinus obstruction syndrome. BCS is an uncommon, potentially fatal condition. Regional differences significantly impact BCS incidence [3]. Among Asian countries, BCS found to be common, diagnosed to cause liver disease in countries such as India, and Nepal, but rare in developed countries [4]. BCS is considered to affect one in 2.5 million people in the West annually. There are also significant disparities between the West and Asia in terms of preferred anatomical sites. In the West, thrombosis primarily affects the hepatic veins; IVC activation is less frequent [5]. IVC is one of primary site of hepatic venous outflow obstruction in among BCS patients in Asian countries [6].

BCS appears as the liver's inflammation and leading to fundamental prothrombotic disorders. The diversity in anatomical location favoring may be explained by geographic disparities in these systematic risks, with poverty being much more prevalent in Asia and combined oral usage and myeloproliferative neoplasia being far more prevalent in the West [7]. As to what the origin of the hepatic venous outflow obstruction, it rapidly results in increased hypotension and hepatic sinus pressure, which causes venous obstruction and ischemia injury to the sinusoidal hepatocytes in the area [8]. If treatment measures or the formation of a venous lateral system do not reduce hepatic sinusoidal tension, nodular renewal, inflammation, and finally cirrhosis take place [9].

After diagnosis of hepatic venous outflow obstruction through magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or computed tomography (CT) [10], there is need to adopt suitable therapeutic options. However, over the last few decades, the advanced biological therapeutic strategies have enhanced survival rates among BCS patients, reported to be 80%-90% in some cases [5, 11]. BCS treatment options comprise orthotopic liver transplantation, decompressing therapies like recanalization techniques

(thrombolytic therapy, endovascular, and angiography), patient treatment with heparin medication, and surgical shunting OLT and TIPS [12].

In this study, we will specifically discuss the TIPS as an obstruction removing technique in which percutaneous image-guided process would pass into the liver parenchyma through creation of portocaval shunt [13]. Due to feasibility and high acceptance rates, TIPS has been recommended as valuable therapeutic in case of severe refractory ascites and variceal bleed [14]. The implication of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)-covered stents has enhanced of the TIPS patency as a standard therapy of BCS. TIPS has reportedly been mentioned as an effective therapy option for BCS [15].

Technically reported, a TIPS surgery is more difficult in a person with BCS than cirrhosis. In medical centers with expertise, the success rate for TIPS implantation in BCS is 80%, opposed to over 90% for cirrhosis [16, 17]. TIPS appears to be a viable option to portosystemic shunting to relieve the liver, particularly since only 18% of individuals are adequately controlled by conventional therapy alone. A maximum of 66.5% of patients still weren't properly managed after adding surgical excision procedures (thrombolytic treatments, angioplasty, or stenting) of short-length impairment to the hospital attention. Presumably, these patients are suited for TIPS implantation [18].

Being heterogenous conditions in Budd Chiari syndrome, the clinical manifestation accounts for acute liver cirrhosis, and failure among asymptomatic patients. Abdominal discomfort is observed by 60% of patients, ascites by 83%, and hepatomegaly by 67%, comprising the traditional triad of abdominal pain, hydrocephalus, and hepatomegaly. Fever, pedal edema, and truncal hepatic veins are further clinical characteristics. Hepatic encephalopathy and gastrointestinal bleeding (3.6%) are less frequent clinical symptoms (9%). About 20% or more of people experience no symptoms at all during initial phase. Using this theory, BCS was divided into four categories: fulminant, acute, subacute, and chronic. The severity and speed of the hepatic venous outflow blockage, as well as the availability of decompressing venous collaterals, determine how BCS manifests [2,19].

In clinical practice, this classification is not particularly useful. Numerous prognostic models have been developed to estimate mortality and susceptibility to treatment interventions in order to get consequences. This rating system utilizes clinicopathological data to categories patients, although it is controversial whether they should be used to manage a specific patient. There is very weak association among prevalence of clinical symptoms and tissue damage caused by obstruction outflow in venous system. Most common symptoms among 50% of patients are cirrhosis or fibrosis, reported as histological influences of chronicity [20].

Very few studies have predicted the good outcomes of TIPS in BCS patients and have rarely reported the enhancement of survival rates after adopting TIPS. To overcome this study gap, we designed this meta-analysis with aim to evaluate the good clinical outcomes of TIPS among Budd Chiari Syndrome. This study will help in adoption of TIPS as an effective and feasible technique for treatment of obstruction outflow in BCS patients.

Materials and methods.

To fulfill aim of study, we conducted meta-analysis following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines to evaluate the efficacy and clinical outcomes of TIPS in Budd Chiari Syndrome (BCS) patients. The collection, extraction and screening of research articles for recent meta-analysis have been summarized through following PRISMA statement flowchart in Figure 1.

The search strategy of recent Meta analysis was followed up by data collection and extraction that was relevant to research aims. The databases used for data collection and search includes PubMed, SCOPUS, ProQuest, MEDLINE, and ScienceDirect on June 30, 2022. The research experts further reviewed each variation in search results to draw a decision. The MeSH keywords used to extract data for recent meta-analysis include “Budd Chiari Syndrome” “outcomes of TIPS” “survival rates after TIPS” and “clinical outcomes of TIPS” in each database.

Fig. 1. Study materials

Study selection.

After extraction of related research articles, the data was selected and screened through following the inclusion and exclusion criteria that are essential components of research. The screening procedure in recent meta-analysis was conducted by using Google Spreadsheet (Google LLC, Mountain View, California, United States). The selected study was related to TIPS as an intervention, control of obstruction outflow in venous system, and clinical outcomes by following PICO criteria, in which population were BCS patients, and outcomes were measured as survival rates and TIPS prognostic index scores. The inclusion criteria for selection

were (1) randomized clinical trials, and prospective studies (2) assessing relation with Budd Chiari syndrome (BCS) (3) implicating TIPS as an intervention or treatment strategy (4) measuring clinical outcomes as survival rates and prognostic index scores (5) written in English

Although the exclusion criteria for recent research were (1) review articles, case studies and other systematic review or meta-analysis (2) studies using animal models, (3) Research articles discussing other intervention measures rather than TIPS in BCS patients.

Quality assessment.

After data selection, the quality of included papers was assessed by using tools of critical appraisal by the Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine (CEBM) of the University of Oxford [24]. Validity, significance, and relevance were the three major parts used for the critical evaluations.

Additionally, we used Cochrane's tool for risk-of-bias to assess the likelihood of bias in seven various areas, including selection bias (random sequence generation and allocation concealment), performance bias (blinding of participants and staff), high turnover bias (incomplete outcome data), identification bias (blinding of outcome assessment), and reporting bias (selective reporting).

Data extraction. For data extraction, we assessed the following characteristics of study including study type, author, study aim, year, research area, population types, sample size, intervention type, primary outcomes and level of evidence, and time for research conductance. The clinical outcomes after TIPS in the recent meta-analysis were recorded in the form of survival rates, OLT free survival rates and prognostic index score. The data was represented in form of tables and forest plots.

Meta-analysis. The quantitative analysis was then performed on all included research. Review Manager (RevMan) Version 5.4 was used to conduct the meta-analysis (2020; The Cochrane Collaboration, London, England). The pooled analysis included all outcomes collected, including survival rates, changes in OLT free survival, and prognostic index scores expressed as odds ratios (OR) and risk ratios (RR). Then, using traditional meta-analysis, summary data and associated 95 percent confidence interval (CI) were produced. In the meantime, fixed-effect inverse variance was used to analyze

survival rates utilizing data of a general inverse variance type using RR effect measures. Forest plots and funnel plots were used to visualize all of the results. The frequency analysis in each study was also examined using the heterogeneity indices that were calculated.

Results.

Following the 3 main inclusion criteria, only 20 papers were up to mark, and fulfilling research aims. Similarly, the 60 paper were excluded from above mentioned 100 due by following exclusion criteria of studies. 40 more papers were excluded during screening, because of repetition in research records. Only about 10 research articles were assessed and well recognized for research criteria. The recent meta-analysis followed the PRISMA standards for data extraction and selection. Based on search strategy, only seven studies found to be eligible out of 67 research articles, as extracted initially from above mentioned databases. According to inclusion and exclusion criteria, only seven studies were discussing implications of intervention of transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) in Budd Chiari syndrome (BCS) patients. The clinical outcomes of included studies were survival rates after TIPS, OLT free survival rates and prognostic index score among BCS patients. Average time period reported for each study was 50 months which is necessary to assess the recovery and recurrence after surgical intervention of TIPS, except the study, Sharma, et al., 2016 which was conducted between 2004 and 2014 for 10 years [31]. To assure consistent qualities for all samples, the study's 26-week result is still included in the outcome that was derived.

We extracted out seven studies that were up to standardized in terms of applicability and validity by following critical appraisal (Table 1).

Tab. 1.

Quality Assessment through features of importance, validity and applicability.

Authors, year	Randomized assignment of patient	Similar characteristics of samples	Equal treatment of samples	Minimal loss-to-follow up analysis	Double-blind analysis	Treatment effect & precision	Internal validity (PICO)	Patient similarity
	IMPORTANCE					Validity	Applicability	
Seijo, et al., 2013 [25]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Hayek, et al., 2017 [26]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	NI	Yes	Unclear	Yes
Sonavane, et al., 2019 [27]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NI	Yes	Yes
Gamanagatti, et al., 2017 [28]	Yes	NI	Yes	NI	NI	Yes	Yes	NI
Wang, Q., et al., 2019 [29]	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NI	Yes	Yes
Hemachandran, et al., 2021 [30]	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	NI	Yes	Unclear
Sharma, et al., 2016 [31]	Yes	NI	Yes	Yes	NI	Yes	NI	Yes

Three studies have shown the Rotterdam score and child Pugh scores in form of clinical outcomes of TIPS

among BCS patients [25, 26, 29]. Patients of these studies have administrated to TIPS intervention and reported their clinical outcomes in form of Rotterdam

score and child Pugh scores for 1-, 3- and 5-year survival rates. The mean difference among groups with TIPS and without TIPS is 1.02 (1.23-1.74) [CI=95%, z= 9.44, I2=98%].

Fig. 2. Forest plot of comparison of TIPS and without TIPS among BCS patients

Fig. 3. Funnel plot of comparison of TIPS and without TIPS among BCS patients

Four studies have represented the survival rates in years as clinical outcomes after TIPS among BCS patients. After comparison of TIPS and without TIPS

among BCS patients, the odds ratio of 0.35 (0.29 - 0.45) measured from forest plot with [CI=95%, Z=9.21, I2=97%]

Fig. 4. Forest plot of comparison of TIPS and without TIPS among BCS patients in terms of survival rates

Fig. 5. Funnel plot of comparison of TIPS and without TIPS among BCS patients in terms of survival rates

Discussion.

Amongst all therapeutic strategies, highest survival rates were reported after TIPS surgical adoptions which was estimated to be high as 42% - 71% for five years and provide OLT-free survival. There is strong correlation among five-year OLT-free survival among BCS patients with conditions of disease in which they are subjected to transplantation [21]. Another more current retrospective study from the United Kingdom (UK) supports the results that TIPS has a positive long-term success rate and that TIPS implementation of quality management is good when utilizing PTFE-covered stents [22]. These integrated data show that TIPS should be used before OLT in patients who are not responding to medical treatment and recanalization therapy. It really should be mentioned that the TIPS centers participating in the research had substantial expertise putting TIPS in BCS patients, with an insertion success rate of 93% [23].

The European retrospective investigation found a cohort with a BCS-TIPS score > 7 and an extremely poor baseline prognosis that would likely benefit more from early OLT than from a TIPS treatment trial [32]. The UK-based retrospective analysis disproves the use of various prognostic indices while confirming that a high BCS-TIPS score is significantly linked to an increase in mortality. These individuals are at an exceedingly high risk, and many of them have hepatic encephalopathy, which causes them to start out with fulminant liver failure. According to a recent follow-up of the EN-Vie cohort, with this stepwise approach, up to 70% of patients who had invasive treatment underwent TIPS and only 22% needed OLT [33].

Conclusions.

In conclusion, the placement of TIPS in patients with primary BCS was associated with a rather significant prevalence of early problems, and endovascular correction or revisions were necessary in 42 percent of patients. According to the findings of our research, high survival rates are connected with TIPS obstruction, particularly in the case of myeloproliferative neoplasms.

Despite this, the secondary patency rate was very close to one hundred percent, and the chances of long-term survival were favourable.

References

1. Janssen HL, Garcia-Pagan JC, Elias E, et al. Budd-Chiari syndrome: a review by an expert panel. *J Hepatol* 2003;38(3):364–371.
2. Valla DC. The diagnosis and management of the Budd-Chiari syndrome: consensus and controversies. *Hepatology* 2003; 38 (4):793–803.
3. DeLeve, L. D., Valla, D. C., & Garcia-Tsao, G. (2009). Vascular disorders of the liver. *Hepatology* (Baltimore, Md.), 49(5), 1729.
4. Plessier, A., & Valla, D. C. (2008, August). Budd-Chiari syndrome. In *Seminars in liver disease* (Vol. 28, No. 03, pp. 259-269). Thieme Medical Publishers.
5. Darwish Murad, S., Plessier, A., Hernandez-Guerra, M., Fabris, F. M., Eapen, C. E., Bahr, M., ... & Janssen, H. (2009). Etiology, management, and outcome of the Budd-Chiari syndrome. *Annals of internal medicine*, 151(3), 167-175.
6. Qi, X., Zhang, C., Han, G., Zhang, W., He, C., Yin, Z., ... & Fan, D. (2012). Prevalence of the JAK2V617F mutation in Chinese patients with Budd-Chiari syndrome and portal vein thrombosis: a prospective study. *Journal of gastroenterology and hepatology*, 27(6), 1036-1043.
7. Qi, X., He, C., Han, G., Yin, Z., Wu, F., Zhang, Q., ... & Fan, D. (2013). Prevalence of paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria in Chinese patients with Budd-Chiari syndrome or portal vein thrombosis. *Journal of Gastroenterology and Hepatology*, 28(1), 148-152.
8. Valla, D. C. (2009). Primary Budd-Chiari syndrome. *Journal of hepatology*, 50(1), 195-203.
9. Menon, K. N., Shah, V., & Kamath, P. S. (2004). The Budd-Chiari syndrome. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 350(6), 578-585.

10. Bolondi, L., Gaiani, S., Bassi, S. L., Zironi, G., Bonino, F., Brunetto, M., & Barbara, L. (1991). Diagnosis of Budd–Chiari syndrome by pulsed Doppler ultrasound. *Gastroenterology*, 100(5), 1324-1331.
11. Murad, S. D., Valla, D. C., De Groen, P. C., Zeitoun, G., Hopmans, J. A., Haagsma, E. B., ... & Janssen, H. L. (2004). Determinants of survival and the effect of portosystemic shunting in patients with Budd–Chiari syndrome. *Hepatology*, 39(2), 500-508.
12. Eapen, C. E., Velissaris, D., Heydtmann, M., Gunson, B., Olliff, S., & Elias, E. (2006). Favourable medium term outcome following hepatic vein recanalisation and/or transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt for Budd Chiari syndrome. *Gut*, 55(6), 878-884.
13. Fidelman, N., Kwan, S. W., LaBerge, J. M., Gordon, R. L., Ring, E. J., & Kerlan Jr, R. K. (2012). The transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt: an update. *American Journal of Roentgenology*, 199(4), 746-755.
14. García-Pagán, J. C., Caca, K., Bureau, C., Laleman, W., Appenrodt, B., Luca, A., ... & Bosch, J. (2010). Early use of TIPS in patients with cirrhosis and variceal bleeding. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 362(25), 2370-2379.
15. Hernández-Guerra, M., Turnes, J., Rubinstein, P., Olliff, S., Elias, E., Bosch, J., & García-Pagán, J. C. (2004). PTFE-covered stents improve TIPS patency in Budd–Chiari syndrome. *Hepatology*, 40(5), 1197-1202.
16. Fitsiori, K., Tsitskari, M., Kelekis, A., Filippidis, D., Triantafyllou, K., & Brountzos, E. (2014). Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt for the treatment of Budd–Chiari syndrome patients: results from a single center. *CardioVascular and Interventional Radiology*, 37(3), 691-697.
17. Boyer, T. D., & Haskal, Z. J. (2010). The Role of Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (TIPS) in the Management of Portal Hypertension: update 2009. *Hepatology (Baltimore, Md.)*, 51(1), 306-306.
18. Garcia-Pagán, J. C., Heydtmann, M., Raffa, S., Plessier, A., Murad, S., Fabris, F., ... & Bosch, J. (2008). Budd–Chiari Syndrome–Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt Group. TIPS for Budd–Chiari syndrome: long-term results and prognostic factors in 124 patients. *Gastroenterology*, 135(3), 808-815.
19. Dang, X., Li, L., & Xu, P. (2014). Research status of Budd–Chiari syndrome in China. *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Medicine*, 7(12), 4646.
20. Baxter, E. J., Scott, L. M., Campbell, P. J., East, C., Fourouclas, N., Swanton, S., ... & Green, A. R. (2005). Acquired mutation of the tyrosine kinase JAK2 in human myeloproliferative disorders. *The Lancet*, 365(9464), 1054-1061.
21. Ulrich, F., Pratschke, J., Neumann, U., Pascher, A., Puhl, G., Fellmer, P., ... & Neuhaus, P. (2008). Eighteen years of liver transplantation experience in patients with advanced Budd–Chiari syndrome. *Liver Transplantation*, 14(2), 144-150.
22. Mentha, G., Giostra, E., Majno, P. E., Bechstein, W. O., Neuhaus, P., O'Grady, J., ... & Klempner, J. (2006). Liver transplantation for Budd–Chiari syndrome: a European study on 248 patients from 51 centres. *Journal of hepatology*, 44(3), 520-528.
23. Tripathi, D., Macnicholas, R., Kothari, C., Sunderraj, L., Al-Hilou, H., Rangarajan, B., ... & Olliff, S. (2014). Good clinical outcomes following transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic stent-shunts in Budd–Chiari syndrome. *Alimentary pharmacology & therapeutics*, 39(8), 864-872.
24. Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., ... & Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Systematic reviews*, 10(1), 1-11.
25. Seijo, S., Plessier, A., Hoekstra, J., Dell'Era, A., Mandair, D., Rifai, K., ... & European Network for Vascular Disorders of the Liver. (2013). Good long-term outcome of Budd–Chiari syndrome with a step-wise management. *Hepatology*, 57(5), 1962-1968.
26. Hayek, G., Ronot, M., Plessier, A., Sibert, A., Abdel-Rehim, M., Zappa, M., ... & Vilgrain, V. (2017). Long-term outcome and analysis of dysfunction of transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt placement in chronic primary Budd–Chiari syndrome. *Radiology*, 283(1), 280-292.
27. Sonavane, A. D., Amarapurkar, D. N., Rathod, K. R., & Punamiya, S. J. (2019). Long term survival of patients undergoing TIPS in Budd–Chiari syndrome. *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Hepatology*, 9(1), 56-61.
28. Gamanagatti, S. R., Patel, A. H., Kedia, S., Nayak, B., Gunjan, D., Ranjan, G., ... & Acharya, S. K. (2017). Long-term outcomes of transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt in Indian patients with Budd–Chiari syndrome. *European Journal of Gastroenterology & Hepatology*, 29(10), 1174-1182.
29. Wang, Q., Li, K., He, C., Yuan, X., Luo, B., Qi, X., ... & Han, G. (2019). Angioplasty with versus without routine stent placement for Budd–Chiari syndrome: a randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet Gastroenterology & Hepatology*, 4(9), 686-697.
30. Hemachandran, N., Acharya, S., Kedia, S., Gunjan, D., Saraya, A., Sharma, R., & Gamanagatti, S. (2021). Long-Term Outcomes of Endovascular Interventions in More than 500 patients with Budd–Chiari Syndrome. *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*, 32(1), 61-69.
31. Sharma, V. K., Ranade, P. R., Marar, S., Nabi, F., & Nagral, A. (2016). Long-term clinical outcome of Budd–Chiari syndrome in children after radiological intervention. *European Journal of Gastroenterology & Hepatology*, 28(5), 567-575.
32. Senzolo, M., Cholongitas, E. C., Patch, D., & Burroughs, A. K. (2005). Update on the classification, assessment of prognosis and therapy of Budd–Chiari syndrome. *Nature Clinical Practice Gastroenterology & Hepatology*, 2(4), 182-190.
33. Yang, C., Xu, K., Zheng, J., Ma, P., Hu, C., Li, S., ... & Zhang, L. (2014). Hepatocellular carcinoma in Budd–Chiari syndrome: Enhancement patterns at dynamic gadolinium-enhanced T1-weighted MR imaging. *Cell biochemistry and biophysics*, 70(1), 661-666.